

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“TAGAY LANG, DILI MAG MARITES”

If I could, then I would, well, I shouldn't be
Drinking alcohol is part of our reality
It builds tensions, sometimes tons of misery
Dili mag-maoy, dapat happy

Pero kung nay tagay sa gawas, hala, sige bira
Pasagdi kay kinabuhi dawn a nila
Lipay karon, mahay pagka unya
Pato ug manok, bahugan kada kadlawon
Tagay pa more, mao man kaha ang kalipayon

Red Horse, Bacardi, ug Tanduay Ice, lami tanan
Pulos makabarag, makahubog
Whiskey, Lambanog, ug Tuba, walay makapildi
Tagay lang dili mag-meresi
Istoryang malipayon lang, No to sa “Unsay latest”
Tagay lang, dili mag marites